

FACTORS AFFECTING THE CAPITAL STRUCTURE OF MICROFINANCE INSTITUTIONS: AN INSIGHT FROM ISLAMIC RURAL BANKS IN INDONESIA

I Q A'yun¹, M A Afandi²

¹ Economics, Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas Gadjah
indanazulfa1495@gmail.com

² Islamic Economics and Finance, Islamic Middle East Studies, Universitas Indonesia
afandianif@gmail.com

Abstract

Optimal capital structure is the comparison or balance of using capital in long-term by the company which can be shown from the comparison of long-term debt toward its own capital. Capital structure is extremely important in the company in which affecting funding decision and the company performance. Therefore, capital structure is interesting topic to further study. Then, this study is conducted by sampling 157 Islamic rural banks operating in Indonesia in the period 2010 – 2016 with quarterly data to examine the determinants of Islamic rural banks capital structure. A panel regression technique is applied using fixed effect model to estimate the relationship between growth, profitability, bank size, and asset structure as independent variables toward capital structure as dependent variable. The results show that asset structure is statistically significant affecting the capital structure accordance to the pecking order theory, trade theory, costs bankruptcy theory, and agency theory. However, growth is not significant affecting the bank capital structures. Then, the profitability and bank size have negative and significant effect to capital structure. These results can be used to the bank managers to understand the effect of each independent variable to capital structure in the process of decision-making.

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1. Introduction

Capital is one of the production factors used by a company to fund its operational activities and also as a buffer fund (capital buffer) for the chance of failure that will occur in company activities. Capital is a very important element in a company including banking. Even in banks, capital is used as an indicator to measure the level of bank soundness. According to Fatmawati (2015), company capital can be obtained through internal sources and external sources of the company. Internal sources of capital include sources of share capital, retained earnings and reserves. While external sources of capital are obtained from debt with other parties.

Based on the capital sources mentioned above, company management is required to maximize the combination of capital sources whether using internal resources (equity) or external sources (debt) with an optimal portion. According to Fauziah and Iskandar (2015), the determination of the use of capital is a difficult decision for a financial manager, especially for the element of debt because the use of debt will increase the company's leverage. The larger portion of debt usage in the capital structure will cause an increase the company's financial risk if the company is unable to repay funds

due to bankruptcy. In addition, the use of debt as capital must consider the benefits of future debt usage costs (Ramadhini, 2017).

The policy in determining the capital structure in a company is ultimately crucial because it can affect the company's performance and value in the eyes of investors. Capital structure must be arranged optimally with careful consideration so not harm all stakeholders. According to the trade off theory or balancing theory the capital structure is said to be optimal if it can balance the trade off between benefits or returns with the risk or cost of the issued capital.

Islamic Rural Bank (BPRS) is a type of Islamic bank operating in Indonesia other than Islamic Commercial Banks (BUS). BPRS is classified as a financial institution with a target of micro customers. According to the Deposit Insurance Coverage (2017), throughout 2016 DIC has liquidated 10 BPRS in East Java provinces consisting of 3 banks, West Sumatra consisting of 2 banks, West Java consisting of 2 banks, Yogyakarta consisting of 1 bank, South Sulawesi consisting of 1 bank, and Southeast Sulawesi consisting of 1 bank. Based on the press release issued by the Financial Services Authority (FSA) the revocation of the BPRS's business license is generally caused by the management of the bank's management who are unable to comply financial performance, one of which is capital.

From the above facts, it is indicated that there is over leverage in the BPRS capital structure as a result of excessive risk taking carried out by the BPRS management to expand the business. Over leverage in the banking system both in the positions recorded on the balance sheet and off-balance sheet is the forerunner of the 2008 crisis which affects the value of the company (asset prices), bank capital resilience, credit contraction, making a losses both in the internal bank and have a domino effect on the economy as a whole (OJK, 2014). After the crisis, finally emerged a new ratio, namely leverage ratio within the Basel III framework (BIS, 2010).

Therefore, this research is important to be done to determine the factors that influence of the BPRS capital structure other than capital standards (CAR) in the provisions issued by the FSA, namely the Financial Services Authority Regulation Number 66/POJK.03/2016 about the Minimum Capital Requirement and Minimum Core Capital Fulfillment of Islamic Rural Banks that will be effective in January 2020. This research can be taken into consideration for BPRS managers that the variables used have a significant influence on the BPRS capital structure in decision-making process in the arrangement of optimal capital structure.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Static-Trade-Off Theory

Modigliani and Miller models originated from the debate that the market value of an enterprise depends on its capital structure, based on the premise of thinking that the capital structure does not affect the company's cash flow (Kyereboah-Cleman, 2007). The trade off model states that firms in determining capital structure will pay attention to the trade off between the benefit of using debt in the form of tax shield and reducing agency costs from shareholders, but this will lead to the cost of bankruptcy and agency. The guidelines are used as a basis in the selection of capital structure that is when the marginal value of the benefits of issuing debt can offset the increase in the value of present value arising from issuing debt (Myers, 2001).

2.2. Pecking Order Theory

This theory illustrates that companies will prefer to use their internal funding first instead of using external funding. The selection of external funding is based on the lowest level of risk.

Companies that use earnings are held up in funding companies will have a positive impact on the company, as this indicates that the company is in a state of profit. So that will affect the stock price increase. In the case of a company that prioritizes debt as the main source of funding, then this will have an impact on the decline in stock prices.

2.3. Agency Theory

According to Jensen and Meckling (1976), this agency theory is based on two conflicts, between (1) managers and shareholders, (2) creditor and shareholder. The agency problem form there are three, the first form is agency problem which occurs between managers and shareholders, this conflict occurs because shareholders who have a desire for high returns, while managers aim to increase the growth and size of the company. The second form of problem is the agency problem between shareholders and creditors arising from moral dangers. The third form of conflict is the agency problem that occurs between the company and the consumer. Conflict occurs when the consumer as a principal, then the company will provide the best service to every consumer for loyalty always awake. So the reputation of the company depends on the assessment of the services provided to consumers. But when the company as a principal, the consumer can harm the company as a violation of the company's copyright

2.4. Theory Costs Bankruptcy

Bankruptcy fees represent costs incurred after the company is declared bankrupt. Bankruptcy costs consist of two types: direct and indirect. Direct bankruptcy costs are administrative costs, attorneys' wage fees, court fees, etc. to be paid by the company. The indirect cost of bankruptcy is an economic loss due to bankruptcy as time is wasted taking care of the problem. Companies that become financial distress and large bankruptcy costs tend to reduce leverage (Amelitta, 2008). Banking capital structure is determined by various factors, both internal and external factors.

Several factors affecting the structure of banking capital that comes from internal banks are profitability, growth, assets structure and size:

2.5. Growth

According to the pecking order theory that firms with high growth require larger funds and funds sourced from corporate internal funds are insufficient to offset the company's growth, which in turn will require a larger external fund. Different studies with this research are Jensen and Meckling (1976), Kim and Sorensen (1986), and Titman and Wessels (1988), the same results also found by Auerbach (1985) also argue that leverage is inversely proportional to growth rate because the tax deductions on interest payments are less valuable for fast-growing firms because fast-growing firms have non-debt tax shields. In contrast, Michaelas et al (1999) found future growth to be positively related to leverage and long-term debt.

2.6. Profitability

Profitability can be measured by return on assets (ROA), the higher the ability of a company to gain profit, then the company in finance its business tend to use funds sourced from internal company. But on the one hand, banks that have the ability to gain high profits, will tend to owe greater than companies that have low profits, this is because companies that have a large profit, have the ability to pay larger debts and less risk of bankruptcy.

As for some research results about the effect of profit on capital structure, among others, Myers (1984) prescribes a negative relationship between debt and profitability on the basis that successful companies do not need to depend so much on external funding. But there are other studies that conclude that there is a positive relationship between profit and capital structure ie research conducted by Amidu (2007) and Ahmad et al. (2011) found positive relation between leverage and profitability because of less probability of failure profitable firms demand more debt and can get better conditions (Panno, 2010). Following the arguments given in the pecking order theory we hypothesize that; H1: Banks with higher profitability tend to have low leverage.

2.7. Size

According to Handayani (2011) states that the larger the size of the company, the easier the company to obtain debt, and large companies also have a greater leverage rate than small companies. According to Martin et al., (1988) found that there is a positive relationship between company size and capital structure.

2.8. Asset Structure

According to Atmaja (2003) states that the asset is a property owned by the company, which consists of current assets (asset) and fixed assets (fixed assets). According to Myers (1977) that tangible assets owned by large companies can support higher levels of debt than intangible assets. Companies may use assets as collateral so as to reduce potential agency costs; associated with the use of debt (Smith and Warner, 1979).

3. Research Methodology

3.1. Data

The type of data in this study is secondary data from the BPRS annual financial report obtained from the official website of the Financial Services Authority (FSA). The research period used is quarter data from 2010 to 2016. The research sample used is BPRS operating in Indonesia as many as 157 banks.

3.2. Variable

Variables used are divided into two, namely dependent variable and independent variable. The dependent variable in this study is the capital structure with the proxy used is leverage, and the independent variable used consists of profitability, growth, asset structure, and size. Table 1 below explains the definition of variables, in which the variables used in most studies are derived from comparative results in previous empirical studies.

Table 1. Definition of Variables

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Proxy</i>	<i>Definition</i>
<i>Leverage</i>	Lev_{it}	Total liabilities _t / total assets _t
<i>Growth</i>	$Growth_{it}$	$Asset_t - asset_{t-1} / asset_{t-1}$

<i>Profitability</i>	Prof _{it}	Net profit after taxes _t / total assets _t
<i>Size</i>	Size _{it}	Log of total assets _t
<i>Asset structure</i>	Asset _{it}	Fixed assets _t / total assets _t

The entire variables used are based on the book value. This is in accordance with Myers's (1984) opinion which states that the proper proxy for those variables is the book value of each indicator so that it actually reflects the true value.

3.3. Model

This research uses quantitative approach in analyzing factors affecting BPRS capital operating in Indonesia. In conducting this quantitative analysis used econometric tool by using regression panel method. This study uses panel data techniques i.e. pooled ordinary least square, fixed effect and random effect to estimate the effects of bank-specific variables on leverage (a proxy of capital structure) of Islamic rural banks. In the simplest case in which there are no bank-specific and time-specific effects, the pooled OLS is most appropriate. The fixed effects method allows the intercept for each banks and time periods. On the other hand, random effects method indicates that variation across bank is assumed to be random and uncorrelated with explanatory variables. Moreover, Hausman test used to choose which one panel econometric technique either fixed effects or random effects best explains the estimations. The null hypothesis underlying the Hausman test is that the fixed effects and random effects estimators do not differ substantially. The regression is expressed as:

$$Y_{it} = \beta_{1i} + \beta_2 X_{1it} + \beta_3 X_{2it} + \beta_4 X_{3it} + \beta_5 X_{4it} + \mu_{it}$$

The subscript *i* denotes the cross-sectional dimension, *t* represents the time-series dimension, *y_{it}* represent the dependent variable in the model and β_{1i} is the *y*-intercept. X_{1it} is a 1 x *K* vector of obseravtions on *K* explanatory variables for the *i* bank in the *t* period. $\beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4,$ and β_5 are *K* x 1 vector of parameters and μ_{it} is a disturbance term. The variables are X_1 is growth, X_2 is profitability, X_3 is size and X_4 is asset structure.

4. Empirical Result

4.1. Descriptive Statistics

Table 1 shows the statistical descriptive of all the variables used in the study. The average of the leverage from the bank sampled is 4.22, while the maximum value of the leverage variable is 2.69. Then for growth variable, the average growth of rural banks in Indonesia is 0.053, with maximum value equal to 1.32, and minimum value equal to -0.687. While for profit variable, the average profit of rural banks is 0.0021, with maximum and minimum value of 969 and -3388. As for the variable size, the average size of rural banks in Indonesia is 7.26, with a maximum and minimum value of 8,861 and 5.75. then for asset structure variable has an average of 0.052, with maximum and minimum value of 0.518 and 0.0000694.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics of All Variables

	Leverage	Growth	Profitability	Size	Asset Structure
Mean	4.22E-10	0.053767	0.002139	7.260202	0.052622
Median	1.37E-10	0.040783	1.000000	7.218697	0.041966
Maximum	2.69E-08	1.325559	969.0000	8.861366	0.518687
Minimum	0.000000	-0.687178	-3388.000	5.757631	0.000694
Std. Dev.	1.02E-09	0.127959	66.13920	0.485162	0.044052
Skewness	11.35237	1.835135	-40.19049	0.330035	4.879557
Kurtosis	222.2571	15.74538	2124.655	3.456522	41.85316
Jarque-Bera	6626349.	23990.50	6.15E+08	87.83962	218855.7
Probability	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
Sum	1.38E-06	175.9787	7.000000	23762.64	172.2332
Sum Sq. Dev.	3.43E-15	53.57443	14313015	770.1691	6.349688
Observations	3273	3273	3273	3273	3273

Source: data processed, 2017

4.2. Correlation Analysis

Table 3. Correlation Matrix of All Variables Used in The Study

	Growth	Profitability	Size	Asset Structure
Growth	1.000000	0.044332	0.035058	-0.119014
Profitability	0.044332	1.000000	0.051307	-0.024921
Size	0.035058	0.051307	1.000000	-0.304891
Asser Structure	-0.119014	-0.024921	-0.304891	1.000000

Source: data processed, 2017

From table 2 it can be seen that the highest correlation between independent variables is 0.3, i.e. the relationship between asset structure and size. This means that there is no multicollinearity between independent variables, because the highest correlation is small from 0.7.

4.3. Regression Results and Discussion

Hausman test is used to determine the best model between model of Fixed Effect and Random Effect. The hypothesis proposed is as follows: H_0 : Random Effect model better H_a : Fixed Effect model is better If Probabilita from Chi-square > 0.05 then H_0 accepted model used Random Effect. But if probability < 0.05 then the model used is Fixed Effect. Based on table 3, it can be seen that the probability of Chi-square (0.0105), ie small from α (0.05). it can be concluded that the best model that can be used is fixed effect.

Table 4. Hausman Test Results

Correlated Random Effects - Hausman Test			
Equation: Untitled			
Test cross-section random effects			
Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	13.168633	4	0.0105

Source: data processed, 2017

The results of fixed effect regression analysis can be obtained as follows:

Table 5. Fixed Effect Analysis Results

Variabel Dependent : Leverage				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
Profitability	-4.78E-13	2.33E-13	-2.052275	0.0402
Growth	-1.82E-10	1.24E-10	-1.465060	0.1430
Struktur_Aset	3.62E-09	6.79E-10	5.327623	0.0000
Size	-7.03E-10	9.26E-11	-7.587090	0.0000
C	5.34E-09	6.82E-10	7.828250	0.0000
Prob F-Stat	0.000			
Adj R-Squared	0.306550			

Source: data processed, 2017

Based on the results of data analysis using Eviews program then obtained the regression equation as follows:

$$Y = 5.34 - 4.78 \textit{profit}_{it} - 1.82 \textit{Growth}_{it} + 3.62 \textit{Struktur_Aset}_{it} - 7.03 \textit{Size}_{it}$$

4.4. Discussion

4.4.1 Effect of profit on leverage

From the results of hypothesis testing found that the profit (ROA) significant effect on leverage, this is because profitability has a value of prob (0.0402) < α (0.05). Besides profitability has a coefficient of - 4.78, meaning that when there is a profitability increase of 1%, then the rural banks will decrease the debt of 4.78%. The results of this study in the same direction with research conducted by Myers (1984) which states that there is a negative relationship between debt and profitability on the basis that successful companies do not need to depend so much on external funding.

4.4.2 Effect of Growth on Leverage

From table 5 can be seen that the probability value of growth i.e. 0.1430 > α (0.05), meaning H_0 is not rejected. So there is no significant influence between the growth of rural banks on debt, based on the results of this study can be concluded that the growing level of rural banks,

does not affect the leverage of banks. The results of this study contradict the results of research conducted by Michaelas et al (1999) found future growth positively associated with leverage and long-term debt.

4.4.3 Effect of Asset Structure to Leverage

From table 5 it can be seen that the asset structure has a significant effect on leverage, it can be seen from the probability value of asset structure i.e. $0.0000 < \alpha (0.05)$, with coefficient value of 3.62. This means when a 1% increase in assets, it will increase the debt of 3.62. The results of this study are supported by research conducted by Myers (1977) which states that tangible assets in large quantities can support higher levels of debt.

4.4.4 Effect of Size on Leverage

In table 5 can be seen that size has a negative and significant effect on leverage. Because the probability value of $0.0000 < \alpha (0.05)$ with a coefficient of -7.03. This indicates that when company size increases 1%, then leverage will decrease by 7.03%. The results of this study contradict the research conducted by Martin et al., (1988).

5. Conclusions

Based on the results of the above study concluded that profit has a negative and significant effect on leverage. This is because when profit of rural banks is higher then the ability to pay debt is also high, so it will decrease the need for external funds to finance the company's operations. While the variable growth, in this study did not have a significant effect, meaning there is no influence between the growth of rural banks with the level of debt. While asset structure variables significantly affect leverage, this is because tangible assets in large quantities can support higher levels of debt. While the variable size has a negative and significant effect on leverage.

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